

Socialization of Squid Nugget Making to Increase Creativity in Batu Bara Regency

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Abstract

Indonesia has great potential in fisheries, including marine products such as squid, especially in Batu Bara Regency. However, the use of squid by coastal communities is still limited to simple processing, so the economic value of this product has yet to be optimal. This socialization program for making squid nuggets aims to increase people's creativity in processing squid into products with high selling value. The service method used is the Community-Based Research (CBR) approach. This program actively involves the community in the entire process, from planning to evaluation, to ensure the relevance and sustainability of the program using this approach, including technical training for making squid nuggets, recipe innovation sessions, and product marketing strategy. This training was carried out by practitioners and experts in food processing and marketing. The results of this service show a significant increase in the community's knowledge and skills in processing squid into squid nuggets. Apart from that, there has been increased creativity, which can be seen from the various product innovations produced. Independent business groups were also formed, which could produce and market squid nuggets with consistent quality. Increasing community income from the squid nugget business is an indicator of the success of this program. In conclusion, the socialization program for making squid nuggets has succeeded in increasing coastal communities' creativity and economic welfare. However, to achieve long-term sustainability, it is necessary to pay attention to environmental aspects and expand the program's scope to widen its impact.

Keywords

Nuggets; Socialization; Squid

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INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is a maritime country rich in marine products, including squid. However, squid use in the processed food industry at the community level still needs to be improved. Many people only process squid in simple forms, such as fried or used as

a mixture in cooking (Budiman & Said, 2021). Squid has great potential to be used as a processed food product with high economic value, including squid nuggets. Squid nuggets are attractive in terms of taste and have high nutritional value (Ayorbaba et al., 2019). Batu Bara Regency is one of the districts in North Sumatra Province, Indonesia. Batu Bara Regency is an expansion of Asahan Regency, where seven sub-districts were reduced and moved to become Batu Bara Regency area. This regency is located on the shores of the Malacca Strait, about 175 km south of the capital, Medan.

In addition, most of the residents in coastal areas have a livelihood to meet their living needs by utilizing natural resources in coastal areas, such as rice field farmers, fishermen, and pond farmers. This can be understood as strengthening naturally coastal areas that have abundant natural resource potential. Experience proves that coastal activities have great potential to revive the real sector; this is proven when an economic crisis occurs, and activities in coastal areas get double the profits (Wardhana, 2020). However, the community still needs to gain knowledge and skills in processing squid into processed food products with high selling value (Musa et al., 2024). In addition, the lack of creativity in developing processed products from squid raw materials makes the economic potential of this seafood cannot be utilized to the fullest (Fitriyah & Ansori, 2022). This situation is exacerbated by the need for more socialization and training on processed food product innovation among the community, especially in coastal areas in Batu Bara Regency.

It is interesting to observe that although Indonesia is rich in marine resources, many coastal communities live close to these resources and live in the middle to lower economic conditions. Therefore, teaching people to use marine products, such as squid, in processed products with high selling value can be a solution to improve their welfare (Muchlashin et al., 2022). As one of the innovative products, squid nuggets offer economic value and high nutritional value, which can improve a healthy diet among coastal communities in Batu Bara Regency.

As a first step to creating the preconditions for policy reorientation, one of the ways to save coastal areas is to utilize the sea results. With very diverse marine resources, of course, they can be used by the Indonesian people to improve the economy (Cahyani et al., 2018). Later, it will help the fishing community's economy with good processing efforts by using fishermen's products at sea. One of the things that will be managed and given an example by researchers for fishermen is squid, which is very easy, and many are obtained by fishermen in the sea, namely by screening so that the results obtained are very large.

Increasing Local Economic Potential Through Innovation in Processing Squid into Nuggets in Batu Bara Regency. Batu Bara Regency, as an area rich in marine resources, especially squid (cuttlefish), has great potential to be developed in the food industry. However, the obstacles in processing squid into value-added products still need to be improved, affecting the potential of the local economy and creativity in the food industry. Through the socialization of making squid nuggets, it is hoped to increase people's knowledge and skills related to food processing, as well as inspire innovation in the use of local raw materials. This step is expected to open up new opportunities for micro and small business actors in Batu Bara Regency to develop more diverse and competitive food products in the local and regional markets.

Improving the standard of living of coastal communities can be done by optimizing the use of coastal resources, such as the processing of fishery products (Muttar & Outside, 2022). One of them is that squid contains important minerals, namely sodium, potassium, phosphorus, calcium, magnesium, and selenium. As well as vitamins B1, B2, B12, niacin, folic acid, and fat-soluble vitamins (A, D, E, K). Squid (*Loligo sp.*) is a fishery commodity caught by many fishermen in the waters (Ayorbaba et al., 2019). Efforts to extend shelf life and improve taste can be made by processing these food ingredients.

With processing, one type of food can be made into a variety of products with different tastes. One of these processed products is Nugget. Nuggets are processed products of ground meat that are molded, cooked, and frozen with the addition of certain permitted ingredients (Naufalin et al., 2013). Nuggets are in great demand by the public because they are considered practical and have a fairly high nutritional value (Hayati et al., 2023). Community service previously focused more on using marine products in general without emphasizing specific processed product innovations. Many programs only focus on basic processing techniques without teaching how to create products that are unique and competitive in the market (Hidayatunnikmah et al., 2022; Nugroho et al., 2023). In addition, the need for continuous training and effective mentoring is one of the obstacles to the success of previous programs.

The purpose of the socialization of squid nugget making in Batu Bara Regency is to increase people's creativity in food processing, especially in processing squid into value-added products. Through this activity, the community can expand knowledge and skills related to squid processing and be inspired to innovate in the use of local raw materials. Thus, this socialization is hoped to open up new opportunities for micro and small business actors in Batu Bara Regency to develop more diverse and competitive food products in the local and regional markets. The results of previous research

(Firdaus et al., 2021) stated that based on the business feasibility analysis, the business of making squid nuggets if developed, will be classified as a business worth trying.

The benefit of this service activity for the people of Batu Bara Regency is the increase in knowledge and skills in processing squid into nuggets, which can open up new opportunities for micro and small business actors to develop more diverse and competitive food products. In addition, the diversification of food products can also improve the local economy and positively contribute to creativity in the food industry. The impact of this service activity on the community is the creation of an improvement in the local economy through the production and marketing of squid nuggets and the sustainable use of local natural resources

METHODS

The Community-Based Research (CBR) method is very suitable for the socialization program of making squid nuggets to increase people's creativity. CBR is a collaborative research approach that directly involves the community in every stage of research, from planning to implementation and evaluation (Collins et al., 2018). Through CBR, the community is an object of service and an active partner in the development and problem-solving process. In the context of the socialization of squid nugget-making, the CBR approach begins with a joint planning stage between the community service team and the local community. The initial discussion was conducted to identify the community's needs, potentials, and obstacles in processing marine products, especially squid. The community is involved in formulating training objectives and methods per local conditions and market potential.

This activity was carried out in Lalang Village, Medang Deras District, Batu Bara Regency. The implementation of the activity will be carried out in May - June 2024. During the implementation phase, the community actively participated in training to make squid nuggets. This training covers technical aspects such as raw material selection, processing techniques, and product packaging, as well as non-technical aspects such as marketing strategies and small business management. This participatory approach ensures that the knowledge and skills gained are truly relevant and applicable to society. Program evaluations are carried out collaboratively by involving the community to provide feedback and suggestions for improvement. The results of this evaluation are used to improve training methods and future product development strategies.

a. Implementation Flow Diagram

b. Manufacturing Process

Material:

- Squid and remove the head and ink bag, wash it thoroughly, and then cut it into pieces
- 12 red cayenne peppers (if you want to use spicy spices)
- 200 g teaspoon brown sugar
- 100 gr white sugar (for sweet shredded sugar)
- 300 ml santan
- 1/4 cup condensed acid
- Four tablespoons oil for sautéing

Fine Spices:

- Four red chili peppers (when spicy)
- Three cloves garlic
- 1/2 teaspoon shrimp paste
- Four shallots
- Daun salam
- Salt to taste

How to Make Sweet Shreds:

- The squid is cut into squid swallows. The head and ink bag are removed from the entire body and then cut into small pieces. Next, it is washed with clean water to free it from dirt and residual blood.
- The squid that has been prepared above is weighed 5kg, or whatever you want.
- Boil the pieces of squid in boiling water for 30-60 minutes.
- After cooling, mash the boiled squid with a cook and pestle, then separate the fibers using a fork. However, to make the results more optimal and easy, you can use a shredded machine.
- Weigh the spices needed: 25g coriander, 125g hazelnuts, 350g brown sugar, 150g onion, 50g garlic, and 200g table salt.
- Mash the spices that have been weighed one by one until smooth, mix, and stir until everything is homogeneously mixed, then sauté with a little cooking oil in a pan.
- Coconut, then grate and squeeze it by adding enough hot water.
- Put the resulting coconut milk in a pan, add to it the shredded squid meat and the prepared spices, stir until evenly distributed, then heat on the stove until dry and drain on top.
- Heat as much as 0.5kg of cooking oil in a pan on the stove over medium heat; put the prepared squid in it little by little, and fry until dry and light brown, then drain and cool on top.
- Pack the resulting shredded in plastic bags or other packaging.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The socialization of making squid nuggets has increased people's knowledge and skills in processing squid into processed products with high selling value. Before this program was implemented, many people only knew how to process squid. After participating in the training, they can now process the squid into squid nuggets that are not only delicious but also have an attractive appearance and are in accordance with hygiene and health standards. The training, which includes raw material selection techniques, manufacturing processes, and packaging, has provided a comprehensive understanding to participants.

This program has also encouraged increased creativity and innovation among the community. Through discussion sessions and hands-on practice, participants are encouraged to experiment with various spices and additives to create a variety of unique squid nuggets with different flavors. Some participants have even started to

develop squid nugget recipes with local touches, such as using spices typical of their region, which gives their products their own uniqueness.

One of the significant results of this program is the formation of several independent business groups that focus on the production and marketing of squid nuggets. These groups are producing squid nuggets for local consumption and are starting to explore a wider market through online marketing and cooperation with local stores. The ongoing mentoring of the service team assists these groups in developing effective business strategies, managing finances, and maintaining consistency in product quality.

The existence of independent efforts in the production of squid nuggets has had a positive impact on increasing people's income. Some participants reported an increase in their household income after engaging in the squid nugget business. With the increase in income, the welfare of families has also improved, as seen from their ability to meet better basic needs and the opportunity to send children to higher education.

The results of this activity can be seen from the process and response from the community during the process. After the entire series of PKM activities were implemented, the knowledge and skills of the people of Lalang Village, Batu Bara District, in innovating local products increased. The results of this service activity went smoothly, as expected. This can be seen from the enthusiasm of the Lalang village government from the beginning to the end of the activity, as well as the training participants, listening to all the material presented and interactive. The process of delivering the material also went smoothly. The service team provided materials processed a few days before the socialization activity began to streamline training time. For partners to better understand, the service team provided a simulation of making Squid nuggets through a video displayed during the activity. This activity was closed with distributing Squid nugget products to the community. The following is a picture of the implementation of service activities by the team:

Figure 1. Materials and tools for the implementation of service

Figure 2. Socialization of community service activities

The analysis of the results of this service shows significant progress in improving the knowledge and skills of the people of Batu Bara Regency in processing squid into nuggets. Compared to previous community service research results, there was a clear increase in active participation from all stakeholders, including squid fishermen, micro-entrepreneurs, and other local communities. The community can be directly involved in the research and action process, which positively impacts the service program's effectiveness (Fanjoy & Bragg, 2019; Putrie et al., 2024). This analysis can also be juxtaposed with theories related to community development and innovation in the food industry, which is an analytical knife to evaluate the impact and potential for further development of the squid nugget-making socialization program in Batu Bara Regency.

In terms of the local economy, the results of this service also show a significant increase in the diversification of food products and the improvement of the local economy. With the production of more diverse and competitive squid nuggets, micro and small business actors in Batu Bara Regency have new opportunities to develop their businesses (Asfahani et al., 2023; Suryanti et al., 2024). This analysis can be

sharpened by using local economic theories and micro-business development, which will provide deeper insights into the potential for local economic growth through innovation in food processing (Amri et al., 2024; Herry et al., 2019). Thus, the results of this service provide direct benefits in improving community knowledge and skills and positively impact the sustainable development of the local economy.

The socialization of making squid nuggets to increase community creativity has a number of interesting findings when compared to previous service programs and relevant theoretical studies (Mildawati et al., 2023; Ruck et al., 2021). Previous programs that focused on developing processed seafood products often provided only basic technical training without encouraging significant innovation or creativity from participants (Gosdin et al., 2021; Wahyuniar et al., 2024). This causes the products produced to tend to be homogeneous and lack added value that can compete in a wider market.

In contrast to the previous findings, this socialization program succeeded in encouraging participants to innovate and create various more creative squid nugget products. The training covers technical aspects such as processing and packaging techniques and emphasizes the importance of creativity in developing new recipes and marketing strategies (Putrie et al., 2024; Rizki & Wahdah, 2022). This is in line with the theory of innovation put forward by Schumpeter (1934), which states that innovation is key in the entrepreneurial process and can include the introduction of new products or new production methods (Judijanto et al., 2022; Lestari et al., 2022). In addition, the Community-Based Research (CBR) approach used in this program also contributes significantly to its success. According to Stringer (1996), CBR emphasizes the importance of active community participation in every stage of research to produce relevant and sustainable solutions. In this program, the community is involved from the planning stage to the evaluation so that they feel they own the program and are more motivated to develop their business (Agdal et al., 2019; Singgalen et al., 2019). This active participation also allows for a more effective transfer of knowledge and skills, in accordance with the experiential learning theory from Kolb (1984), which states that learning occurs through direct experience.

Another finding that supports the success of this program is the increase in the income of the communities involved. Before participating in the training, most people only had basic knowledge of processing squid, and their income was relatively low. After the training, they were able to produce squid nuggets with high selling value, which had a direct impact on increasing household income (Yunda Sari et al., 2020). This supports the theory of the creative economy, which states that creativity and

innovation can be valuable economic assets that can improve people's welfare (Chambers & Conway, 1992). The squid nugget products produced have economic value and high nutritional value, providing double benefits for the community.

The program's sustainability evaluation shows that the independent business groups formed can maintain product quality consistency and develop effective marketing strategies. This success not only has a positive economic impact but also a social impact by strengthening community bonds and creating new jobs (Saha, 2023). According to the sustainability theory of Elkington (1997), sustainability includes economic, social, and environmental aspects. This program has been successful in economic and social aspects, but to achieve full sustainability, it is also necessary to pay attention to environmental aspects, such as the sustainable use of squid raw materials. So, this squid nugget-making socialization program has shown that the right approach, namely by combining technical training, encouragement to innovate, and active community participation, can increase the creativity and economic well-being of the community. This success emphasizes the importance of integration between theory and practice in the development of community service programs, as well as the need for a comprehensive and sustainable approach to achieve maximum results.

CONCLUSION

Conclusion the service program for making squid nuggets to increase community creativity has succeeded in achieving its goals by providing comprehensive training and encouraging innovation among participants. The community not only gains technical skills in processing squid but is also empowered to create a variety of unique products with high selling value. The positive impact of this program can be seen from the increase in community income, the formation of independent business groups, and the contribution to improving community nutrition through healthy squid nugget products, providing benefits in the form of improving the local economy, diversifying food products, and utilizing natural resources. This is expected to open up new opportunities for MSME actors to develop more diverse and competitive food products to significantly impact the Batu Bara Regency's people in optimizing marine resources. In this service, several weaknesses still need to be addressed. Some of them include a lack of active participation from all related parties, Limited resources, and a Lack of support from related parties. By identifying and overcoming weaknesses or shortcomings that have not been achieved, this service program can continue to develop and provide greater benefits for the people of Batu Bara Regency.

REFERENCES

- Agdal, R., Midtgård, I. H., & Meidell, V. (2019). Can asset-based community development with children and youth enhance the level of participation in health promotion projects? A qualitative meta-synthesis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(19), 3778.
- Amri, M., Asfahani, A., Kadeni, K., Arif, M., & Jamin, F. S. (2024). Community Empowerment In The Fields Of Education Entrepreneurship And The Environment In The Village. *Community Development Journal: Jurnal Pengabdian Masyarakat*, 5(2), 3704–3712.
- Asfahani, A., Tono, M., & Sain Zohaib Hassan. (2023). Land Optimization to Improve the Economy through Attractive Tourist Destinations in Smart City Indonesia. *International Assulta of Research and Engagement (IARE)*, 1(2), 87–98.
- Ayorbaba, A. E., Widiastuti, N., Ananta, A. S., & Boli, P. (2019). Biological Aspects of Squids (*Ioligo* sp.) Caught by Fishermen in Manokwari Waters. *Jurnal Sumberdaya Akuatik Indopasifik*, 3(1), 65. <https://doi.org/10.46252/jsai-fpik-unipa.2019.vol.3.no.1.67>
- Budiman, D. R. S. M. Y., & Said, D. (2021). Manajemen Tata Kelola Maritim Kepulauan Seribu sebagai Kawasan Strategis Nasional dalam Perspektif Keamanan Maritim. *Jurnal Maritim Indonesia (Indonesian Maritime Journal)*, 9(3), 281–298.
- Cahyani, F. A., Winarno, D. W., & Sudarwanto, A. S. (2018). Upaya Pengelolaan Wilayah Pesisir Dalam Mewujudkan Perlindungan Dan Konservasi Di Taman Pesisir Ujungnegoro-Roban Kabupaten Batang. *Jurnal Hukum Dan Pembangunan Ekonomi*, 6(2), 203–221. <https://doi.org/10.20961/hpe.v6i2.17754>
- Chambers, R., & Conway, G. R. (1992). Sustainable rural livelihoods: practical concepts for the 21st century. *IDS Discussion Paper*, 296.
- Collins, S. E., Clifasefi, S. L., Stanton, J., Straits, K. J. E., Gil-Kashiwabara, E., Rodriguez Espinosa, P., Nicasio, A. V, Andrasik, M. P., Hawes, S. M., & Miller, K. A. (2018). Community-based participatory research (CBPR): Towards equitable involvement of community in psychology research. *American Psychologist*, 73(7), 884.
- Fanjoy, M., & Bragg, B. (2019). Embracing complexity: Co-creation with retired immigrant women. *Gateways: International Journal of Community Research and Engagement*, 12(1), ID-6342.
- Firdaus, M., Dwi Argo, B., Iriany, A., Septimawan Sutopo, D., Ariyanto, D., & Andan Prasetyo, M. (2021). Pelatihan Pembuatan Nugget Cumi dan Kelayakan Usahanya di Desa Air Bini, Kecamatan Siantan, Kabupaten Kepulauan Anambas. *Prosiding Simposium Nasional VIII Kelautan Dan Perikanan*, 23–28.
- Fitriyah, R. D., & Ansori, T. (2022). Diversifikasi Pengelolaan Hasil Tangkap Nelayan Dusun Kaligung Pasuruan sebagai Upaya Ketahanan Ekonomi Keluarga Pesisir.

- Amalee: Indonesian Journal of Community Research and Engagement*, 3(2), 425–442. <https://doi.org/10.37680/amalee.v3i2.2093>
- Gosdin, L., Sharma, A. J., Tripp, K., Amoafu, E. F., Mahama, A. B., Selenje, L., Jefferds, M. E., Martorell, R., Ramakrishnan, U., & Addo, O. Y. (2021). A School-Based Weekly Iron and Folic Acid Supplementation Program Effectively Reduces Anemia in a Prospective Cohort of Ghanaian Adolescent Girls. *Journal of Nutrition*, 151(6), 1646–1655. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jn/nxab024>
- Hayati, R., Mayani, N., Husna, R., & Sulaiman, I. (2023). Pengolahan Nugget Ayam dan Penerimaannya Melalui Uji Organoleptik di Desa Krueng Lam Kareung Kecamatan Indrapuri Aceh Besar. *Jurnal Pengabdian Mahakarya Masyarakat Indonesia*, 1(1), 19–24. <https://doi.org/10.24815/pemasi.v1i1.30198>
- Herry, E., Permana, P. Y. E., Aji, W. B., & Muhtadi, R. (2019). Total Quality Management Development and Sharia Governance Efforts in Sharia Micro Financial Institutions to Improve Market Share. *IJIEEB International Journal of Integrated Education, Engineering and Business* EISSN 2615-1596 PISSN 2615-2312, 2(1), 27–35.
- Hidayatunnikmah, N., Nuraini, I., Latifah, A., & Ningrum, N. P. (2022). Pelatihan pembuatan minuman kekinian boba herbal untuk immune booster pada remaja di masa pandemi Covid-19. *INDRA: Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat*, 3(1), 19–23. <https://doi.org/10.29303/indra.v3i1.140>
- Judijanto, L., Asfahani, A., & Krisnawati, N. (2022). The Future of Leadership: Integrating AI Technology in Management Practices. *Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Development*, 1(2), 99–106.
- Lestari, R., Pradani, T., & Digdowiseiso, K. (2022). The Effects of Digital Marketing, Entrepreneurship Orientation, and Product Innovation on Competitive Advantage and Its Impact on the Marketing Performance of Talas Bolu Sangkuriang in Bogor City. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute-Journal (BIRCI-Journal)*, 5(1), 2081–2087.
- Mildawati, R., Nugroho, B. P., Prasetyawan, F., Kristijono, A., Saristiana, Y., Oktadiana, I., & Imran, A. K. (2023). Virtual socialization about the use of family medicinal plants as an alternative for treatment. *Assoeltan: Indonesian Journal of Community Research and Engagement*, 1(2), 99–106.
- Muchlashin, A., Putri, W. A., Asya'bani, N., & Nurfajrin, S. (2022). Pemberdayaan Ekonomi Masyarakat Nelayan di Kampung Mumes Raja Ampat Papua Barat. *Amalee: Indonesian Journal of Community Research and Engagement*, 3(2), 235–249. <https://doi.org/10.37680/amalee.v3i1.1562>
- Muchtar, F., & Bahar, H. (2022). Edukasi Pembuatan Nugget Ikan Sebagai Upaya Pemanfaatan Potensi Perikanan di Desa Mekar Kecamatan Soropia Kabupaten Konawe. *ABDIKAN: Jurnal Pengabdian Masyarakat Bidang Sains Dan Teknologi*, 1(4), 526–533. <https://doi.org/10.55123/abdikan.v1i4.1118>

- Musa, M., Rahman, R., & Asfahani, A. (2024). Strengthenation Of The Role Of The Family In Building The Basis Of Children's Moral Education; An Empowered Family Approach. *Community Development Journal: Jurnal Pengabdian Masyarakat*, 5(3), 4108–4115.
- Naufalin, R., Erminawati, & SR, H. (2013). Aplikasi pengawet alami buah kecombrang (*Nicolania speciosa*) pada nugget ayam. *Jurnal Agroteknologi*, 7(2), 187–195.
- Nugroho, A. P., Asfahani, A., Sugiarto, F., Sufyati, H. S., & Setiono, A. (2023). Community Assistance in Utilizing Sharia-Based Digital Banking. *Amalee: Indonesian Journal of Community Research and Engagement*, 4(2), 519–530.
- Putrie, R. A., Asfahani, A., Harati, R., & Dewi, R. A. P. K. (2024). Community Assistance In Communication Skills Development Training Programs. *Community Development Journal: Jurnal Pengabdian Masyarakat*, 5(3), 4848–4856.
- Rizki, S. N., & Wahdah, N. (2022). Training of the Art Reading Al Qur'an of Sidomulyo Community at Tumbang Tahai Village. *International Journal of Community Engagement Payungi*, 2(1), 43–50.
- Ruck, M. D., Hughes, D. L., & Niwa, E. Y. (2021). Through the looking glass: Ethnic racial socialization among children and adolescents. *Journal of Social Issues*, 77(4), 943–963.
- Saha, M. (2023). English teachers' attitudes towards learners: Effects on the rural pedagogies in Bangladesh. *Ampersand*, 10, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amper.2022.100107>
- Singgalen, Y. A., Sasongko, G., & Wiloso, P. G. (2019). Community participation in regional tourism development: a case study in North Halmahera Regency-Indonesia. *Insights into Regional Development*, 1(4), 318–333.
- Suryanti, S., Rofiah, C., Asfahani, A., Cindy, A. H., & Palayukan, H. (2024). Optimization Community Progress Through Empowerment In The Field Of Sustainable Education. *Community Development Journal: Jurnal Pengabdian Masyarakat*, 5(2), 3640–3646.
- Wahyuniar, W., Asfahani, A., Suyuti, S., & Sitopu, J. W. (2024). Community Engagement In Education: Fostering Sustainable Impact Through Outreach Initiatives. *Community Development Journal: Jurnal Pengabdian Masyarakat*, 5(3), 4116–4124.
- Wardhana, I. (2020). Ruang Kawasan Industri Oleochemical Maloy Kutai Timur ; (Sebuah Telaah Kritis). *Jurnal Renaissance*, 5(01), 599–609.
- Yunda Sari, F., Sapta Pranoto, Y., Purwasih, R., Agribisnis, J., & Pertanian Perikanan dan Biologi, F. (2020). Analysis of Salted Fish (Case Study of Rebo Village, Sungailiat District, Bangka District) Analisis Usaha Ikan Asin (Studi Kasus Desa Rebo Kecamatan Sungailiat Kabupaten Bangka). *Jurnal of Integrated Agribusiness*, 2(1), 20–36. <https://doi.org/10.33019/jia.v2i1.xxxx>